

From molecules to material via a polynitrogen precursor[†]

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Abstract : Starting from aromatic polynitrogen systems like N_4^{2-} and N_6^{4-} , several potential molecular materials have been generated, with suitable linkers. Necessary optimization and frequency analysis have been performed at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d) and B3LYP/6-31G(d) levels of theory. Conceptual density functional theory based reactivity descriptors and the nucleus independent chemical shift values lend additional insights into their stability, reactivity and aromaticity. They may be considered to be suitable candidates for hydrogen storage material.

Keywords : Polynitrogen, aromaticity, functional material, conceptual DFT.

1. Introduction

The study of polynitrogen¹ molecules and their associated doped clusters²⁻⁶ has emerged as an important and progressing area of research for more than two decades. This is mainly because of their use as high energy density materials (HEDM)⁷⁻¹³. Further, several theoretical investigations revealed that the metal doped polynitrogen clusters can be used as potential storage materials for hydrogen, a clean fuel. Among them the square planar N_4^{2-} ring is an interesting system as has been reported by Zandwijk *et al.*¹⁴. The square planar N_4^{2-} ring has 6π electrons confirming aromaticity according to $(4n + 2)$ rule for aromaticity. However, Chattaraj *et al.*¹⁵ have reported a conflicting aromaticity for N_4^{2-} system (σ -antiaromatic and π -aromatic). Among the polynitrogen compounds, planar benzene-like N_6 molecule has been investigated theoretically¹⁶. Vogler⁷ has given an experimental evidence for this system. Though the hexagonal N_6 molecule contains 6π electrons in its outermost orbital it is a non-planar system and is stable in the D_2 symmetric twist-boat structure whereas N_6^{4-} molecule is planar and it contains 10π electrons and hence follows Huckel's rule of the aromaticity. Li *et al.*¹⁷ have studied the N_6^{4-}

system theoretically and have found a weak aromaticity of the system at HF/4-31G level of theory. Importantly Duan and Li¹⁸ have shown the existence of planar D_{6h} symmetric N_6^{4-} with a second order saddle point on PES at the B3LYP/6-311+G(d) level of theory. However, in our previous work we have reported¹⁵ a local minimum on PES for this system when no diffuse function is used. Furthermore, the planar aromatic N_6^{4-} ring exhibits negative NICS(0) values.

In the present work we have theoretically designed a new functional material¹⁹⁻²³ taking N_4^{2-} and cyclopropenyl cation ($C_3H_3^+$) as parent moieties and also have designed some large molecular clusters of N_6^{4-} which are linked by aromatic B_4^{2+} ring. This material may play an important role in diverse chemical processes like hydrogen trapping, CO_2 scavenging, etc.

The cyclopropenyl cation²⁴ ($C_3H_3^+$) is a well established aromatic system having two delocalized π electrons. In the first step we have produced a neutral moiety $N_4C_3H_2$ (C_{2v} symmetry) from the ($C_3H_3^+$) and N_4^{2-} rings, which is considered to be the basic functional unit in this study. In the next step we follow the same procedure once again to produce $(N_4C_3H)N_4C_3H_2$. After three suc-

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

cessive steps we obtain $(N_4C_3H)_4N_4C_3H_2$. In the final step we further add another functional unit to $(N_4C_3H)_4N_4C_3H_2$ to achieve a planar crown like closed ring structure $(N_4C_3H)_6$. This planar ring corresponds to D_{6h} symmetry. Extension to three dimensions may also be attempted to obtain novel molecular materials.

The N_6^{4-} and B_4^{2+} rings form a complex $N_6B_4^{2-}$ system. We have considered $N_6B_4^{2-}$ system as our parent moiety and have formed 3 to 7 membered rings by gradual addition of this moiety. We have optimized all the rings (3-7 membered) by considering them as neutral species. The total charge attributed to the ring is zero. The stability and reactivity of all these molecular species are analyzed with the aid of various conceptual density functional theory²⁵⁻²⁸ (CDFT) based global reactivity descriptors like electronegativity^{29,30} (χ), hardness^{31,32} (η) and electrophilicity³³⁻³⁶ (ω) and also some local reactivity descriptors like Fukui function^{37,38} ($f(r)$) and philicity^{39,40} (ω_k^α).

The aromaticity of the $(N_4C_3H)_6$ (crown structure), N_6^{4-} and B_4^{2+} rings is evaluated through the calculation of the nucleus independent chemical shift⁴¹ (NICS) value computed at the centre of the rings.

2. Theoretical background

In general, a stable molecular system in its ground state is characterized by its existence at the minimum on the potential energy surface (PES). This condition of stability may be complemented by the concepts of maximization in hardness⁴²⁻⁴⁷ (η) and minimization in polarizability⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ (α) and electrophilicity^{52,53} (ω).

For an N -electron system having total energy E , the electronegativity^{29,30} (χ) and hardness^{31,32} (η) can be defined as follow :

$$\chi = - \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(r)} = - \mu \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(r)} \quad (2)$$

where $v(r)$ and μ are external and chemical potentials

respectively. Electrophilicity³³⁻³⁶ (ω) is defined as

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} = \frac{\chi^2}{2\eta} \quad (3)$$

Applying the finite difference approximations to eqs. (1) and (2), χ and η can be expressed as

$$\chi = \frac{I + A}{2} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\eta = I - A \quad (5)$$

where I and A are the ionization potential and electron affinity of a system respectively and are computed using the energies of the N -electron system with energy $E(N)$. They may be expressed as follow :

$$I = E(N - 1) - E(N) \quad (6)$$

$$A = E(N) - E(N + 1) \quad (7)$$

The local reactivity descriptors like Fukui function^{37,38} ($f(r)$) and philicity^{39,40} (ω_k^α) help us to assess the site selectivity during a chemical reaction. Fukui function can be interpreted either as the change in the electron density ($\rho(r)$) at each point r due to an infinitesimal change in the number of electrons (N) at fixed $v(r)$ or as a change in the system's chemical potential due to an infinitesimal change in the external potential ($v(r)$) at a particular point r for a fixed N , i.e.,

$$f(r) = \left(\frac{\partial \rho(r)}{\partial N} \right)_{v(r)} = \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial v(r)} \right)_N \quad (8)$$

Condensation of this Fukui function ($f(r)$), to an individual atomic site k in a molecule gives rise to the following expressions

$$f_k^+ = q_k(N + 1) - q_k(N) \text{ for nucleophilic attack (9a)}$$

$$f_k^- = q_k(N) - q_k(N - 1) \text{ for electrophilic attack (9b)}$$

$$f_k^0 = \frac{[q_k(N + 1) - q_k(N - 1)]}{2} \text{ for radical attack (9c)}$$

where q_k represents the electron population on the k -th atom.

The corresponding philicities are defined as

$$\omega_k^\alpha = \omega \cdot f_k^\alpha \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha = +, -$ and 0 represents nucleophilic, electrophilic and radical attacks respectively.

3. Computational details

The molecular geometries of $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_n$ - $N_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters (shown in Fig. 1) are optimized and characterized at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level of theory whereas the planar N_6^{4-} and

B_4^{2+} systems and their corresponding $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and $(N_6B_4)_{3-7}$ clusters are optimized at the same level of theory without any diffuse function by using the GAUSSIAN03 program⁵⁴ suite. Harmonic vibrational frequency analysis is also performed for all the structures at the same level of theory. The number of imaginary frequency (NIMAG) values for all the optimized geometries turns out to be zero confirming their existence at minima on

Fig. 1. Optimized geometries (B3LYP/6-31+G(d)) of different $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters

the potential energy surface (PES). The single point calculations for all the structures are performed to evaluate the energies of $(N \pm 1)$ electron systems considering the geometries of the corresponding optimized N -electron systems. The I and A values are calculated using the Δ SCF technique. The electronegativity^{29,30} (χ), hardness^{31,32} (η) and electrophilicity³³⁻³⁶ (ω) are calculated using eqs. (4), (5) and (3) respectively. The calculations of atomic charges (Q_k) and the Fukui function ($f(r)$) are carried out

adopting the natural population analysis (NPA) scheme. The NICS(0) values are calculated at the centres of the $(N_4C_3H)_6$, N_6^{4-} and B_4^{2+} rings.

4. Results and discussion

The optimized geometries for $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_n$ - $N_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ along with their symmetry point groups are illustrated in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 depicts the optimized geometries of the N_6^{4-} , B_4^{2+} moi-

Fig. 2. Optimized geometries (B3LYP/6-31G(d)) of different N_6^{4-} , B_4^{2+} , $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n = 3-7$) clusters.

eties and their corresponding $N_6B_4^{2-}$, $(N_6B_4)_n$; $n=3-7$ complexes. All these structures correspond to minima on the potential energy surface at the used level of theory (since the NIMAG values are zero).

Geometrical parameters and global and local reactivity descriptors for these systems are presented in Tables 1-6. Tables 1 and 4 present the associated geometrical parameters like bond length and bond angle of the sys-

tems. The dihedral angles of $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1, 3, 4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters are zero, which confirms the planarity of the structures except $(N_4C_3H)_2N_4C_3H_2$ where two dihedral angles are slightly greater than zero. All the N-C bond lengths and N-N-C bond angles are equal in $(N_4C_3H)_6$ cluster as expected from symmetry. In case of the $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n = 3-7$) clusters, with an increase in the ring size the interatomic distances vary slightly. The bond

Table 1. Bond lengths and bond angles of $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters

	Bond lengths (Å)	Bond angles (°)	Dihedral angles (°)
		$N_4C_3H_2$	
N-N	N2-N3=N2-N1=1.321, N3-N4=N4-N1=1.461	N2-N1-N4=85.658, N1-N2-N3=100.56	N1-N4-C3-C2 =0.000
C-C	C3-C1=C3-C2=1.415, C1-C2=1.333	N1-N4-C3=135.94	
N-C	N4-C3=1.271		
		$(N_4C_3H)N_4C_3H_2$	
N-N	N2-N1=N2-N4=1.324, N1-N3=N3-N4=1.453, N6-N8=N8-N7=1.394, N5-N6=1.389, N6-N8=1.394	N2-N1-N3=N2-N4-N3=85.728, N6-N5-N7=82.969, N6-N7-N8=82.700, N4-N3-C5=135.26, N8-N7-C3=131.95	N4-N3-C5-C4=0.000, N8-N7-C3-C1=0.000
C-C	C5-C6=1.420, C5-C4=1.396, C4-C6=1.364, C3-C2=1.419, C3-C1=1.419, C1-C2=1.332, N3-C5=1.281, N6-C6=1.317		
N-C	N7-C3=1.295		
		$(N_4C_3H)_2N_4C_3H_2$	
N-N	N10-N9=1.456, N10-N12=1.323, N9-N11=1.457, N12-N11=1.322, N2-N1=1.389, N1-N4=1.375, N2-N3=1.383, N3-N4=1.368, N8-N6=1.401, N8-N7=1.396, N5-N6=1.412, N7-N5=1.409	N2-N1-N4=82.62, N2-N3-N4=83.09, N8-N6-N5=83.01, N5-N7-N8=83.34, N12-N10-N9=85.72, N12-N11-N9=85.72, N10-N9-C3=135.06, N1-N2-C1=131.37, N1-N4-C6=131.55, N6-N8-C4=131.43, N5-N6-C8=131.32	N11-N9-C3-C1=0.02, N2-N3-C3-C1=0.01, N3-N4-C6-C4=0.00, N7-N8-C4-C6=0.00, N7-N5-C8-C9=-0.06
C-C	C3-C1=1.420, C3-C2=1.400, C2-C1=1.356, C6-C4=1.456, C6-C5=1.343, C5-C4=1.398, C8-C7=1.427, C9-C7=1.329, C9-C8=1.427		
N-C	N9-C3=1.279, N2-C1=1.325, N4-C6=1.329, N8-C4=1.288, N5-C8=1.278		
		$(N_4C_3H)_3N_4C_3H_2$	
N-N	N10-N12=1.407, N12-N11=1.406, N11-N9=1.401, N9-N10=1.406, N14-N13=1.389, N14-N16=1.393,	N10-N12-N11=N4-N1-N2=83.12, N14-N16-N15=N5-N6-N8=82.91,	N12-N11-C11-C10=0.00, N16-N14-C12-C10=0.00, N16-N15-C9-C8=0.00,

Table-1 (contd.)

	N16-N15=1.394, N15-N13=1.390, N5-N6=1.394, N6-N8=1.390, N4-N3=1.401, N3-N2=1.406	N1-N2-C1=131.93, N1-N4-C6=131.01, N6-N8-C4=131.03, N6-N5-C8=130.93, N12-N11-C11=131.01	N16-N8-C4-C5=0.00, N1-N4-C6-C5=0.00, N1-N2-C1-C2=0.00
C-C	C11-C12=1.44, C10-C12=1.367, C9-C8=1.446, C9-C7=1.378, C4-C5=1.367; C4-C6=1.443, C1-C3=1.431, C1-C2=1.432, C3-C2=1.327		
N-C	N2-C1=1.280, N4-C6=1.291, N8-C4=1.309, N5-C8=1.305, N15-C9=1.305, N14-C12=1.309, N11-C11=1.291		
		(N ₄ C ₃ H) ₄ N ₄ C ₃ H ₂	
N-N	N1-N2=1.324, N3-N4=1.455, N1-N4=1.454, N8-N6=1.380, N8-N7=1.387, N6-N5=1.386, N19-N20=1.392, N20-N18=1.391, N17-N19=1.388, N15-N16=1.398, N13-N14=1.397, N14-N16=1.400, N12-N10=1.368, N11-N14=1.374, N12-N11=1.371	N14-N13-N15=82.79, N9-N10-N12=82.79, N2-N1-N4=82.79, N5-N6-N8=82.79, N18-N20-N19=82.79, N14-N16-N15=83.32, N9-N11-N12=83.32, N2-N3-N4=83.32, N5-N7-N8=83.32, N18-N17-N19=83.32	N13-N15-C7-C9=0.00, N10-N12-C8-C9=0.00, N10-N9-C3-C2=0.00, N1-N2-C1-C2=0.00, N1-N4-C6-C5=0.00, N6-N8-C4-C5=0.00, N6-N5-C11-C10=0.00, N20-N19-C12-C10=0.00, N20-N18-C15-C13=0.00
C-C	C3-C1=1.420, C3-C2=1.397, C8-C9=1.443, C7-C9=1.373, C15-C14=1.441, C15-C13=1.378, C10-C11=1.408, C12-C11=1.341, C5-C6=1.414, C5-C4=1.432	N13-N15-C7=131.74, N10-N12-C8=131.74, N10-N9-C3=131.74, N1-N2-C1=131.74, N1-N4-C6=131.74, N6-N8-C4=131.74, N6-N5-C11=131.74, N20-N19-C12=131.74, N20-N18-C15=131.74	
N-C	N15-C7=N12-C8=1.303, N9-C3=N2-C1=1.303, N4-C6=N8-C4=1.303, N5-C11=N19-C12=1.303, N18-C15=1.303		
		(N ₄ C ₃ H) ₆ (crown)	
N-N	N1-N2=N1-N4=1.397, N5-N6=N8-N6=1.397, N9-N10=N10-N12=1.397, N13-N14=N13-N15=1.397, N3-N4=N2-N3=1.389, N5-N7=N8-N7=1.389, N15-N16=N18-N17=1.389, N19-N20=N22-N24=N23-N24=1.397, N12-N11=N11-N9=N14-N16=1.389, N17-N19=N21-N22=N21-N23=1.389	N4-N1-N2=N9-N10-N12=82.79, N15-N13-N14=N18-N20-N19=82.79, N22-N24-N23=N5-N6-N8=82.79, N4-N3-N2=N9-N11-N12=83.32, N15-N16-N14=N18-N17-N19=83.32, N22-N24-N23=N5-N7-N8=83.32 N1-N2-C1=N10-N9-C3=131.74, N10-N12-C8=N13-N15-C7=131.74, N13-N14-C15=N20-N18-C13=131.74, N20-N19-C17=N24-N23-C12=131.74,	N1-N2-C1-C2=0.00, N10-N9-C3-C2=0.00, N10-N12-C8-C9=0.00, N13-N15-C7-C9=0.00, N13-N14-C15-C14=0.00, N20-N18-C13-C14=0.00, N20-N19-C17-C16=0.00, N24-N22-C18-C16=0.00, N24-N23-C12-C10=0.00, N6-N5-C11-C10=0.00, N6-N8-C4-C5=0.00,

C-C	C1-C3=C8-C7=C15-C13=1.448, C17-C18=C12-C11=C4-C6=1.448, C17-C16=C12-C10=C4-C5=1.373, C2-C3=C5-C4=C8-C9=C15-C14=1.373	N6-N5-C11=N6-N8-C4=131.74, N1-N4-C6=131.74	N1-N4-C6-C5=0.00
N-C	N2-C1=N9-C3=N12-C8=1.303, N15-C7=N14-C15=N18-C13=1.303, N19-C17=N22-C18=N23-C12=1.303, N5-C11=N8-C4=N4-C6=1.303		

Table 2. Point group (PG), total energy (E , au), electronegativity (χ , eV), hardness (η , eV), electrophilicity (ω , eV) and NICS(0) values for $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters

System	PG	E (au)	χ (eV)	η (eV)	ω (eV)	NICS(0), ppm
$N_4C_3H_2$	C_{2v}	-334.25862	4.450	7.579	1.307	
$(N_4C_3H)N_4C_3H_2$	C_s	-667.90077	4.491	5.134	1.965	
$(N_4C_3H)_2N_4C_3H_2$	C_s	-1001.55167	4.257	3.936	2.302	
$(N_4C_3H)_3N_4C_3H_2$	C_s	-1335.20126	4.074	3.642	2.278	
$(N_4C_3H)_4N_4C_3H_2$	C_s	-1668.85935	3.897	2.889	2.629	
$(N_4C_3H)_6$ (crown)	D_{6h}	-2001.88679	3.725	2.790	2.486	-7.480

Table 3. Charges (Q_N , NPA), Fukui function values for nucleophilic attack (f_N^+) and electrophilic attack (f_N^-) and philicity (ω_N^{ρ}) values for various N-centres of $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ clusters

Clusters	Atoms	Charge (Q_N)	f_N^+	f_N^-	ω_N^+	ω_N^-
$N_4C_3H_2$	N(4)	-0.151	0.028	-0.054	0.037	-0.071
$(N_4C_3H)N_4C_3H_2$	N(3), N(6),	-0.154, -0.075,	0.021, 0.011,	0.018, 0.039,	0.041, 0.023,	0.036, 0.077,
	N(7)	-0.071	-0.026	-0.019	-0.050	-0.037
	N(2), N(4),	-0.082, -0.053,	0.002, 0.019,	0.025, -0.019,	0.004, 0.044,	0.058, -0.045,
$(N_4C_3H)_2N_4C_3H_2$	N(5), N(8),	-0.046, -0.067,	0.021, -0.013,	-0.021, -0.012,	0.049, -0.029,	-0.049, -0.029,
	N(9)	-0.154	0.015	0.014	0.035	0.032
	N(2), N(4),	-0.070, -0.062,	-0.014, 0.003,	-0.007, 0.014,	-0.032, 0.007,	-0.016, 0.031,
$(N_4C_3H)_3N_4C_3H_2$	N(5), N(8),	-0.069, -0.066,	-0.004, 0.009,	0.003, 0.016,	-0.008, 0.021,	0.006, 0.037,
	N(11), N(14),	-0.157, -0.079,	0.010, 0.005,	0.019, 0.017,	0.022, 0.011,	0.043, 0.038,
	N(15)	-0.070	-0.013	-0.004	-0.029	-0.009
	N(2), N(4),	-0.055, -0.080,	0.009, -0.007,	-0.003, 0.011,	0.023, -0.017,	-0.007, 0.029,
$(N_4C_3H)_4N_4C_3H_2$	N(5), N(8),	-0.051, -0.076,	0.018, -0.007,	-0.006, 0.009,	0.047, -0.018,	-0.015, 0.023,
	N(9), N(12),	-0.153, -0.086,	0.007, -0.002,	0.007, 0.007,	0.018, -0.004,	0.020, 0.017,
	N(15), N(18),	-0.053, -0.078,	0.016, -0.007,	-0.006, -0.005,	0.043, -0.018,	-0.015, -0.013,
	N(19)	-0.048	0.007	-0.007	0.019	-0.018
$(N_4C_3H)_6$ (crown)	N(2), N(4),	-0.065, -0.065,	0.007, 0.004,	-0.005, -0.005,	0.017, 0.009,	-0.013, -0.011,
	N(5), N(8),	-0.065, -0.065,	0.007, 0.001,	0.008, -0.002,	0.018, 0.004,	0.020, -0.006,
	N(9), N(12)	-0.065, -0.065,	0.004, 0.007,	-0.004, 0.007,	0.009, 0.016,	-0.010, 0.017,
	N(14), N(15),	-0.065, -0.065,	0.001, 0.007,	-0.002, 0.008,	0.004, 0.018,	-0.006, 0.020,
	N(18), N(19),	-0.065, -0.065,	0.004, 0.007,	-0.005, -0.005,	0.009, 0.017,	-0.011, -0.013,
N(22), N(23)	-0.065, -0.065	0.004, 0.007	-0.004, 0.007	0.009, 0.016	-0.010, 0.017	

Table 4. Bond lengths and bond angles of $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n=3-7$) clusters

	Bond lengths (Å)	Bond angles (°)	Dihedral angles (°)
		$N_6B_4^{2-}$	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1.445, N4-N5=N5-N6=1.377, N1-N6=N3-N4=1.249	N1-N2-N3=109.06, N4-N5-N6=112.32	N1-N2-B2-B4=13.80
B-B	B1-B2=B2-B4=1.641, B1-B3=B3-B4=1.528	N1-N2-B2=124.00	
N-B	N2-B2=1.406		
		$(N_6B_4)_3$	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1.413, N4-N5=N5-N6=1.413, N3-N4=N6-N1=1.243, N7-N8=N7-N9=1.413, N10-N12=N12-N11=1.413, N9-N11=N8-N10=1.243, N13-N14=N13-N15=1.413, N17-N18=N18-N16=1.413, N16-N14=N15-N17=1.243	N1-N2-N3=115.66, N4-N5-N6=115.66, N8-N7-N9=115.66, N10-N12-N11=115.66, N16-N17-N18=115.66, N14-N13-N15=115.66, N5-N4-B3=N3-N2-B6=122.12, N18-N17-B7=N15-N13-B12=122.12, N12-N11-B9=N9-N7-B2=122.12	N4-N5-B3-B1=17.71, N9-N7-B2-B1=17.71, N3-N2-B6-B5=17.71, N17-N18-B7-B5=17.71, N15-N13-B12-B10=17.71, N11-N12-B9-B10=17.71
B-B	B1-B2=B2-B4=1.600, B4-B3=B3-B1=1.600, B5-B6=B6-B8=1.600, B8-B7=B7-B5=1.600, B9-B10=B10-B12=1.600, B12-B11=B11-B9=1.600		
N-B	N7-B2=N5-B3=1.411, N2-B6=N18-B7=1.411, N13-B12=B9-N12=1.411		
		$(N_6B_4)_4$	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1.413, N4-N5=N5-N6=1.413, N3-N4=N6-N1=1.242, N7-N8=N7-N9=1.413, N10-N12=N11-N12=1.413, N8-N10=N9-N11=1.242, N13-N15=N13-N14=1.413, N17-N18=N16-N18=1.413, N14-N16=N15-N17=1.242, N19-N20=N19-N21=1.413, N23-N24=N22-N24=1.413, N20-N22=N21-N23=1.242	N1-N2-N3=115.45, N4-N5-N6=115.45, N7-N8-N9=115.45, N10-N12-N11=115.45, N16-N18-N17=115.44, N14-N13-N15=115.44, N20-N19-N21=115.44, N22-N24-N23=115.44, N2-N3-B6=N5-N4-B3=121.92, N13-N15-B2=N18-N17-B9=121.92, N7-N9-B12=N12-N11-B13=121.92, N19-N21-B16=N24-N23-B7=121.92	N15-N13-B2-B1=21.19, N17-N18-B9-B10=21.19, N9-N7-B12-B10=21.19, N3-N2-B6-B5=21.19, N23-N24-B7-B5=21.19, N21-N19-B16-B14=21.19, N9-N7-B12-B10=21.19, N11-N12-B13-B14=21.19
B-B	B1-B2=B1-B3=1.599, B3-B4=B2-B4=1.599, B5-B6=B6-B8=1.599,		

	B5-B7=B7-B8=1 599, B13-B14=B14-B16=1 599, B13-B12=B12-B16=1 599, B9-B10=B10-B12=1 599, B9-B11=B11-B12=1 599		
N-B	N2-B6=N5-B3=1 413, N13-B2=N18-B9=1 413, N7-B12=N12-B13=1 413, N19-B16=N24-B7=1 413		
		(N ₆ B ₄) ₅	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1 413, N4-N5=N5-N6=1 413, N7-N8=N7-N9=1 413, N11-N12=N10-N12=1 413, N13-N14=N13-N15=1 413, N6-N18=N17-N18=1 413, N19-N20=N19-N21=1 413, N22-N24=N23-N24=1 413, N25-N26=N25-N27=1 413, N29-N30=N28-N30=1 413, N3-N4=N6-N1=1 242, N8-N10=N9-N10=1 242, N14-N16=N15-N17=1 242, N20-N22=N21-N23=1 242, N26-N28=N27-N29=1 242	N1-N2-N3=115 30, N4-N5-N6=115 30, N23-N24-N22=115 30, N21-N19-N20=115 32, N11-N12-N10=115 31, N9-N7-N8=115 31, N29-N30-N28=115 30, N26-N25-N27=115 30, N16-N18-N17=115 31, N12-N13-N15=115 30, N3-N2-B6=N21-N19-B16=121 32, N4-N5-B3=N11-N12-B13=121 35, N3-N2-B6=N9-N7-B12=121 30, N23-N24-B7=N17-N18-B17=121 35, N29-N30-B9=121 34, N27-N25-B20=121 30	N3-N2-B6-B5=-21 81 N4-N5-B3-B1=21 74, N23-N24-B7-B5=21 67 N21-N19-B16-B14=-21 85 N11-N12-B13-B14=21 74 N9-N7-B12-B14=-21 85 N29-N30-B9-B10=21 70, N27-N25-B20 B18=-21 88 N17-N18-B17 B18=21 67 N15-N13-B2-B1=-21 91
B-B	B1-B2=B2-B4=1 598, B4-B3=B3-B1=1 598, B5-B6=B6-B8=1 598, B8-B7=B7-B5=1 598, B13-B14=B14-B16=1 598, B16-B15=B15-B13=1 598, B9-B10=B10-B12=1 598, B12-B11=B11-B9=1 598, B17-B18=B18-B20=1 598, B20-B19=B19-B17=1 598		
N-B	N13-B2=N5-B3=1 415, N2-B6=N24-B7=1 415, B16-N19=B13-N12=1 415, N7-B12=N30-B13=1 415, N25-B20=N18-B17=1 415		
		(N ₆ B ₄) ₆	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1 414, N4-N5=N5-N6=1 414, N7-N8=N7-N9=1 414, N11-N12=N10-N12=1 414, N13-N14=N13-N15=1 414,	N3-N2-N1=N21-N19-N20=115 21, N9-N7-N8=N33-N31-N32=115 21, N27-N25-N26=N15-N13-N14=115 21, N4-N5-N6=N23-N24-N22=115 19, N11-N12-N10=N35-N36-N34=115 19,	N3-N2-B6-B5=-21 78, N21-N19-B16-B14=-21 78, N9-N7-B12-B10=-21 78 N33-N31-B24-B23=-21 78 N27-N25-B20 B18=-21 78

Table-4 (contd.)

	N16-N18=N17-N18=1.414, N19-N20=N19-N21=1.414, N22-N24=N23-N24=1.414, N25-N26=N25-N27=1.414, N29-N30=N28-N30=1.414, N35-N36=N34-N36=1.414, N31-N32=N31-N33=1.414, N3-N4=N6-N1=1.240, N8-N10=N9-N11=1.240, N14-N16=N15-N17=1.240, N20-N22=N21-N23=1.240, N26-N28=N27-N29=1.240, N32-N34=N33-N35=1.240	N29-N30-N28=N15-N13-N14=115.19, N3-N2-B6=N21-N19-B16=120.81, N4-N5-B3=N23-N24-B7=120.77, N11-N12-B13=N35-N36-B9=120.77, N9-N7-B12=N33-N31-B24=120.81, N29-N30-B21=N17-N18-B17=120.77, N27-N25-B20=N15-N13-B2=120.81	N15-N13-B2-B1=-21.78, N4-N5-B3-B1=22.00, N18-N17-B17-B18=22.00, N29-N30-B21-B23=22.00, N35-N36-B9-B10=22.00, N11-N12-B13-B14=22.00, N23-N24-B7-B5=22.00
B-B	B1-B2=B2-B4=1.598, B4-B3=B3-B1=1.598, B5-B6=B6-B8=1.598, B8-B7=B7-B5=1.598, B13-B14=B14-B16=1.598, B16-B15=B15-B13=1.598, B9-B10=B10-B12=1.598, B12-B11=B11-B9=1.598, B17-B18=B18-B20=1.598, B20-B19=B19-B17=1.598, B21-B22=B22-B24=1.598, B24-B23=B23-B21=1.598		
N-B	N13-B2=N5-B3=1.417, N2-B6=N24-B7=1.417, N19-B16=N12-B13=1.417, N7-B12=N36-B9=1.417, N31-B24=N30-B21=1.417, N25-B20=N18-B17=1.417, N13-B2=N5-B3=1.417		
		(N ₆ B ₄) ₇	
N-N	N1-N2=N2-N3=1.415, N4-N5=N5-N6=1.415, N7-N8=N7-N9=1.415, N11-N12=N10-N12=1.415, N13-N14=N13-N15=1.415, N16-N18=N17-N18=1.415, N19-N20=N19-N21=1.415, N22-N24=N23-N24=1.415, N25-N26=N25-N27=1.415, N29-N30=N28-N30=1.415, N35-N36=N34-N36=1.415, N31-N32=N31-N33=1.415, N3-N4=N6-N1=1.240,	N1-N2-N3=N4-N5-N6=115.16, N14-N13-N15=N16-N18-N17=115.16, N26-N25-N27=N28-N30-N29=115.16, N32-N31-N33=N34-N36-N35=115.16, N40-N42-N41=N38-N37-N39=115.16, N8-N7-N9=N10-N12-N11=115.16, N20-N19-N21=N22-N24-N23=115.16, N1-N2-B6=N6-N5-B3=120.36, N14-N13-B2=N16-N18-B17=120.36, N26-N25-B20=N28-N30-B21=120.36, N32-N31-B24=N34-N36-B9=120.36, N41-N42-B12=N6-N5-B3=120.36, N39-N37-B28=N8-N7-B25=120.36,	N1-N2-N6-B5=21.46, N20-N19-B16-B15=21.56, N8-N7-B25-B26=21.53, N41-N42-B12-B11=21.52, N32-N31-B24-B22=21.48, N26-N25-B20-B19=21.47, N16-N14-B13-B2=21.46, N6-N5-B3-B4=-21.48, N16-N18-B17-B19=-21.47, N28-N30-B21-B22=-21.51, N34-N36-B9-B11=-21.48, N39-N37-B28-B26=-21.51, N10-N12-B13-B15=-21.47,

	N8-N10=N9-N11=1.240,	N10-N12-B13=N6-N5-B3=120.36,	N22-N24-B7-B8=-21 49
	N14-N16=N15-N17=1.240,	N20-N19-B16=N22-N24-B7=120.36	
	N20-N22=N21-N23=1.240,		
	N26-N28=N27-N29=1.240,		
	N32-N34=N33-N35=1.240,		
	N39-N41=N38-N40=1.240		
B-B	B1-B2=B2-B4=1.597,		
	B4-B3=B3-B1=1.597,		
	B5-B6=B6-B8=1.597,		
	B8-B7=B7-B5=1.597,		
	B13-B14=B14-B16=1.597,		
	B16-B15=B15-B13=1.597,		
	B9-B10=B10-B12=1.597,		
	B12-B11=B11-B9=1.597,		
	B17-B18=B18-B20=1.597,		
	B20-B19=B19-B17=1.597,		
	B21-B22=B22-B24=1.597,		
	B24-B23=B23-B21=1.597,		
	B25-B26=B26-B28=1.597,		
	B28-B27=B27-B25=1.597		
N-B	N13-B2=N5-B3=1.418,		
	N2-B6=N24-B7=1.418,		
	N19-B16=N12-B13=1.418,		
	N7-B25=N37-B28=1.418,		
	N12-B42=N36-B9=1.418,		
	N31-B24=N30-B21=1.418,		
	N25-B20=N18-B17=1.418		

Table 5. Point group (PG), total energy (E , au), electronegativity (χ , eV), hardness (η , eV), electrophilicity (ω , eV) and NICS(0) values for N_6^{4-} , B_4^{2+} , $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and various $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n = 3-7$) clusters

Clusters	PG	E (au)	χ (eV)	η (eV)	ω (eV)	NICS(0), ppm
N_6^{4-}	D_{6h}	-326.94738	-23.733	9.193	30.635	-9.917
B_4^{2+}	D_{4h}	-98.21205	19.935	7.562	26.277	-28.979
$N_6B_4^{2-}$	C_1	-427.55562	-5.007	6.769	1.851	
$(N_6B_4)_3$	D_{3h}	-1282.96704	5.557	4.185	3.689	
$(N_6B_4)_4$	D_{2h}	-1710.65623	5.546	3.809	4.038	
$(N_6B_4)_5$	C_s	-2138.33910	5.531	3.618	4.228	
$(N_6B_4)_6$	C_{6h}	-2566.01764	5.542	3.409	4.504	
$(N_6B_4)_7$	C_1	-2993.69405	5.548	3.258	4.722	

angles gradually decrease but for the (B-B-B) bond angles which exhibit a marginal increase.

The point group (PG), total energy (E , au), electronegativity (χ , eV), hardness (η , eV) and electrophilicity (ω , eV) values for these clusters are tabulated in Tables 2 and 5. The NICS(0) value for the planar $(N_4C_3H)_6$ ring is

also reported in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the χ , η and ω values of most of these structures are positive. A positive χ value indicates that the system may take some electron upon chemical response. Table 2 also shows that the NICS(0) value for $(N_4C_3H)_6$ ring is negative which suggests an aromatic nature of $(N_4C_3H)_6$. It is also true for

Table 6. Charges (Q_N , (NPA)), Fukui function values for nucleophilic attack (f_N^+) and electrophilic attack (f_N^-) and philicity ($\omega_N^{\pm}$) values for N-centres of $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and various $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n = 3-7$) clusters

Clusters	Atoms	Charge (Q_N)	f_N^+	f_N^-	ω_N^+	ω_N^-
$N_6B_4^{2-}$	N(2)	-0.210	0.009	0.082	0.017	0.152
$(N_6B_4)_3$	N(2), N(5),	-0.396, -0.395,	0.000, 0.000,	0.047, 0.047,	0.000, 0.001,	0.175, 0.175,
	N(15), N(20),	-0.395, -0.396,	0.000, 0.000,	0.048, 0.048,	0.000, 0.001,	0.176, 0.176,
	N(25), N(30)	-0.395, -0.395	0.000, 0.000	0.047, 0.047	0.001, 0.000	0.174, 0.174
$(N_6B_4)_4$	N(2), N(5),	-0.397, -0.397,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.035, 0.035,	-0.004, -0.004,	0.142, 0.142,
	N(15), N(20),	-0.397, -0.397,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.035, 0.035,	-0.004, -0.004,	0.142, 0.142,
	N(25), N(30),	-0.397, -0.397,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.035, 0.035,	-0.005, -0.004,	0.142, 0.142,
	N(35), N(40)	-0.397, -0.397	-0.001, -0.001	0.035, 0.035	-0.005, -0.004	0.142, 0.142
$(N_6B_4)_5$	N(2), N(5),	-0.398, -0.398,	0.000, -0.001,	0.028, 0.028,	0.002, -0.002,	0.119, 0.118,
	N(15), N(20),	-0.398, -0.398,	-0.001, -0.000,	0.028, 0.028,	-0.006, -0.001,	0.116, 0.117,
	N(25), N(30)	-0.398, -0.398,	-0.000, -0.002,	0.028, 0.028,	-0.000, -0.011,	0.118, 0.119,
	N(35), N(40),	-0.398, -0.398,	-0.001, 0.000,	0.028, 0.028,	-0.003, 0.001,	0.120, 0.120,
	N(45), N(50)	-0.398, -0.398	-0.002, -0.001	0.028, 0.028	-0.009, -0.004	0.117, 0.118
$(N_6B_4)_6$	N(2), N(5),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.023, 0.023,	-0.002, -0.004,	0.105, 0.105,
	N(15), N(20),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.023, 0.023,	-0.004, -0.003,	0.106, 0.105,
	N(25), N(30)	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.023, 0.023,	-0.004, -0.003,	0.106, 0.105,
	N(35), N(40),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.023, 0.023,	-0.004, -0.005,	0.105, 0.105,
	N(45), N(50),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.023, 0.023,	-0.004, -0.005,	0.105, 0.105,
	N(55), N(60)	-0.399, -0.399	-0.001, -0.001	0.023, 0.023	-0.002, -0.003	0.105, 0.105
$(N_6B_4)_7$	N(2), N(5),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.003, -0.001,	0.096, 0.096,
	N(15), N(20),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.004, -0.003,	0.096, 0.096,
	N(25), N(30)	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.002, -0.003,	0.097, 0.098,
	N(35), N(40),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.004, -0.003,	0.096, 0.096,
	N(45), N(50),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.002, -0.003,	0.096, 0.094,
	N(55), N(60),	-0.399, -0.399,	-0.001, -0.001,	0.020, 0.020,	-0.002, -0.003,	0.0917, 0.093
	N(65), N(70)	-0.399, -0.399	-0.001, -0.001	0.020, 0.020	-0.002, -0.003	0.094, 0.096

N_6^{4-} and B_4^{2+} as well. As the size increases the system becomes softer and more electrophilic.

The local parameters like charges (Q_k), Fukui functions (f_k^α) and philicity (ω_k^α) values are reported in Tables 3 and 6. We have used natural population analysis (NPA) scheme to calculate the charges and population on N-centres attached to C and B atoms of the clusters. All these N-centres bear a negative charge which indicates that these N-centres are suitable for an attack by a cation or a hard electrophile. In $(N_4C_3H)_6$ all the N-centres attached to C atom bear same amount of negative charge due to symmetry. The most suitable site for soft nucleophilic/electrophilic attack can be assigned by the Fukui function and philicity values. The propensity of attack by a soft nucleophile is not negligible although the N-centres are negatively charged. However, the N-centres in $N_6B_4^{2-}$,

$(N_6B_4)_n$; $n = 3-7$ bear negative charges and are suitable sites for attack by a cation and a hard electrophile as dictated by the atomic charges as well as by a soft electrophile as suggested by their Fukui function and philicity values.

5. Conclusions

Quantum chemical calculations at the B3LYP level using different basis sets on $N_4C_3H_2$, $(N_4C_3H)_nN_4C_3H_2$ ($n = 1-4$) and $(N_4C_3H)_6$ and N_6^{4-} , B_4^{2+} , $N_6B_4^{2-}$ and $(N_6B_4)_n$ ($n=3-7$) reveal that the studied molecules belong to the minima on the potential energy surface (PES). The negative NICS(0) value for the D_{6h} symmetric $(N_4C_3H)_6$ molecule predicts the aromaticity of the system. The D_{6h} symmetry and the associated aromaticity of N_6^{4-} is lost when it forms a complex with B_4^{2+} moiety. The NPA

charge calculations and the associated Fukui function and philicity values show that the N-centres bear negative charges and are apt for an attack by a cation or a hard electrophile as well as by a soft electrophile in all cases.

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